

Class Incremental Learning for Algorithm Selection Supplementary Information

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1 Class Incremental Learning

1.0.1 Parameter regularisation approaches

Elastic Weight Consolidation (EWC)^[3] is a parameter regularisation approach, where the importance of each weight is estimated using the Fisher Information matrix^[4]. These are stored in memory, and during training, changes to important parameters are penalised. In larger models, calculating the Information Matrix can be computationally expensive however.

Memory Aware Synapsis (MAS)^[1] is another parameter regularisation method, where weight importance is calculated based on the sensitivity of the output to small changes in the parameters. When training on a new task, the loss is calculated with respect to the parameter importances.

Finally, in the *Synaptic Intelligence* (SI)^[10] method, weight importance is dynamically calculated during the training of each task by keeping track of the changes to the parameters as well as the loss.

1.0.2 Knowledge Distillation approaches

Learning without Forgetting (LwF)^[5] is a knowledge distillation based method. When learning new classes, the new inputs are run through the last trained model, and the output is used in the loss calculation of the new model to avoid catastrophic forgetting. The method is memory efficient and computationally cheap since it does not require past instances to be saved for future training, and parameter importances are not specifically calculated. The method is therefore both efficient and scalable.

1.0.3 Data Regularization approaches

Gradient Episodic Memory (GEM)^[6] saves a specified number of exemplars from previous tasks and uses these to calculate a gradient. When training on new data, the new gradient is projected to the old one and the loss is minimised to avoid catastrophic forgetting using Quadratic Program constraint satisfaction.

Average Gradient Episodic Memory (AGEM)^[2] works similarly to GEM in saving a specified number of exemplars from previous tasks to memory. However, it does not handle the gradient calculation as a constraint satisfaction problem, rather it projects it using the gradient of the old classes, which is computationally cheaper than GEM.

1.0.4 Data-Replay methods

Feature Replay (FR)^[7] is an exemplar-free method that makes use of Gaussian prototypes to reduce catastrophic forgetting. This method selects features of instances from previous

tasks and uses them in training on new tasks. Specifically, it relies on a technique called Asymmetric Prototype Replay loss (PR-ACE)^[7] that balances between new task data and Gaussian prototypes. This method is useful when it is not possible to save any data from previous tasks.

On the other hand, *Experience Replay*^[9] saves randomly selected exemplars from previous classes to memory and uses them during the training of new classes. This is the simplest CIL method, where the performance of Replay increases with the number of exemplars that are saved to memory.

2 Methodology

2.1 Class Incremental Learning methods parameters

The parameters of the CIL methods can be seen in Table 1. For each training strategy the default values were used from the library, or the values provided in the paper where the method was originally proposed. The implementation of Synaptic Intelligence is different from the originally proposed algorithm in the paper cited above. The modified version used in Avalanche is described in^[8].

Table 1: Avalanche CIL method parameters

LwF		EWC	MAC		SI		Replay	GEM		AGEM	
alpha	temperature	lambda	lambda	alpha	lambda	esp	mem size	mem size	mem strength	mem size	sample size
1	2	0.001	1	0.5	0.2	1.00E-07	100	100	0.5	100	100

References

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